

TRANSCULTURAL NURSING IN ACTION: THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF NURSES TAKING CARE OF INDIGENOUS PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

Nurses routinely care for clients from various ethnic and racial backgrounds, yet the specific experiences of nurses caring for indigenous populations have often been overlooked. This phenomenological study aimed to explore and understand the lived experiences of nurses caring for indigenous clients, particularly in an OB-GYN ward setting, to uncover the challenges they face and the meanings they attribute to these experiences. Using purposive sampling, participants were selected from the OB-GYN wards at a government regional hospital in Tagum City, with a minimum of three years of service. Data were gathered through in-depth interviews conducted at the same facility, and analysis followed Colaizzi's method of qualitative data interpretation. The findings revealed three key themes: *Confronting Realities*, *Bridging Two Worlds*, and *Uniting in Diversity*. These themes reflect the nurses' struggles with language barriers and cultural differences, as well as the realization that patience and empathy are essential in transcultural nursing. By overcoming these challenges, nurses play a vital role in bridging the gap between medical practice and cultural diversity, fostering a deeper understanding and celebration of indigenous cultures in healthcare.

Keywords: *Social Science, Transcultural Nursing, Indigenous People, Phenomenology, Tagum City*

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare providers are increasingly serving clients from diverse indigenous, ethnic, and racial groups, necessitating client-centered systems to deliver optimal care (McCalman et al., 2017). However, disparities persist in healthcare access and treatment for racial and ethnic minorities, leading to negative outcomes such as miscommunication, cultural insensitivity, and, ultimately, discriminatory treatment from the very professionals tasked with providing care (Baquet & Commiskey, 1999; Betancourt, 2006; Brach & Fraserirector, 2000; Collins et al., 1999; Collins et al., 2002; Dreachslin & Myers, 2007; Keppel et al., 2002; Torres-Ruiz et al., 2018; US Department of Health and Human Services, 1998; Stephens et al., 2005). These issues are especially pertinent for indigenous populations, who often face systemic barriers that result in inequitable healthcare experiences.

Globally, the United Nations (2014) estimates that 370 million indigenous people exist across 70 countries. The Philippines is a culturally diverse country with an estimated 14-17 million Indigenous Peoples (IPs) belonging to 110 ethno-linguistic groups. They are mainly concentrated in Northern Luzon (Cordillera Administrative Region, 33%) and Mindanao (61%), with some groups in the Visayas area (De Vera, 2007; UNDP, 2013). These figures highlight the increasing cultural diversity that healthcare providers must navigate, often requiring them to adjust to complex cultural beliefs and practices.

Despite efforts to address these disparities, the healthcare needs of indigenous people are often overlooked, with many indigenous communities facing cultural and language barriers that affect the quality of care they receive (Horrill et al., 2018; Periris et al., 2008; Stephens et al., 2005). These challenges are further compounded by social determinants such as poverty, lack of education, and geographical isolation, which limit access to health services. Indigenous peoples remain one of the most marginalized groups in the Philippines, and they experience significant health inequities, often characterized by poorer health outcomes compared to non-indigenous populations (Stephens et al., 2005; UNDP, 2013).

At a government regional hospital in Tagum City, the healthcare providers, particularly nurses, face the challenge of addressing these inequities. Indigenous clients often bring unique cultural perspectives on health, illness, and treatment, which may differ significantly from the biomedical framework commonly practiced in hospitals. As a result, nurses at the government regional hospital in Tagum City may experience conflicts related to cultural beliefs, language barriers, and differing health practices. This situation demands culturally competent nursing care, which is integral to transcultural nursing—an approach that focuses on providing culturally congruent care to diverse populations (Berman et al., 2016).

Transcultural nursing, pioneered by Madeleine Leininger, emphasizes understanding and integrating patients' cultural backgrounds into care delivery to ensure meaningful and culturally appropriate care. Nurses must navigate complex cultural dynamics, such as cultural care preservation, cultural care accommodation, and culture care repatterning, to

meet the needs of indigenous clients (Alligood, 2014). These strategies help nurses balance cultural respect with clinical care, allowing for better health outcomes and patient satisfaction.

Language barriers pose additional challenges in providing quality care. Miscommunication can result in misunderstandings about diagnoses, treatment plans, and self-care instructions, which can have life-threatening consequences (Meuter et al., 2015). The increasing need for culturally competent care highlights the urgency of addressing communication gaps and fostering mutual understanding between healthcare providers and indigenous clients (Betancourt et al., 2002). This complexity is reflected in the experiences of nurses who must negotiate these challenges daily.

Given the significant role that indigenous peoples play in the cultural fabric of the Philippines, the experiences of nurses caring for these populations warrant closer examination. Despite the hospital's efforts to address healthcare inequities, there is limited research on the lived experiences of nurses caring for indigenous patients. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the challenges and insights of nurses at said hospital who care for indigenous clients, offering a deeper understanding of how transcultural nursing principles are applied in real-world settings.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this phenomenological study is to explore the essence of transcultural nursing as experienced by nurses providing care to indigenous clients. Specifically, this research aims to delve into the lived experiences of these nurses, uncovering the unique challenges, difficulties, and rewards they encounter while caring for indigenous people. By focusing on the daily interactions and cultural exchanges between nurses and their indigenous clients, this study seeks to illuminate the complexities of providing culturally competent care. It aims to reveal not only the barriers and hardships, such as language differences, cultural misunderstandings, and resource limitations, but also the joys and fulfillment that arise from bridging cultural divides, fostering mutual understanding, and making a meaningful impact on the health and well-being of indigenous populations. In doing so, this study aspires to contribute valuable insights into the practice of transcultural nursing, highlighting the vital role nurses play in addressing healthcare disparities and promoting culturally sensitive care.

Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of nurses who are taking care of indigenous clients?
2. How do these experiences mean to them?
3. What insights can the participants share with their peers and the nursing practice in general?

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

This study employed a phenomenological research design, which is well-suited for uncovering and describing phenomena as they are experienced by individuals (Creswell, 2013). Phenomenology was chosen for this research because it provides a framework to explore and understand the lived experiences of nurses engaged in transcultural nursing. Specifically, this approach allowed for an in-depth examination of the personal and professional experiences of nurses caring for indigenous clients, shedding light on how they navigate the challenges, joys, and complexities of this unique caregiving context. By focusing on the subjective experiences of the participants, the phenomenological design enables the researcher to gain a deeper understanding of the cultural, emotional, and practical dimensions of transcultural nursing in action.

Setting

The study was conducted at a government regional hospital located in Barangay Apokon, Tagum City, Davao del Norte, a tertiary-level government hospital. With a 600-bed capacity, the hospital provides a wide range of services, including Medical, Surgical, OB-GYN, Pediatrics, Neuro-Ortho, Family Medicine and Palliative Care, Oncology, Hemodialysis, and Public Health services. Notably, this hospital is recognized as a pioneering hospital in the region for its commitment to serving indigenous populations from neighboring tribes and communities. These include the Badjaos, Igorots, Lumads, Mangyans, and various other indigenous groups. This diverse patient demographic makes this hospital a critical setting for exploring transcultural nursing, as nurses regularly encounter clients with distinct cultural practices, languages, and health beliefs. The hospital's role in serving these indigenous populations provides a rich backdrop for understanding the lived experiences of nurses navigating the complexities of culturally sensitive care. The study was conducted from January 2018 to March 2018.

Participants

The study employed purposive sampling to select participants who were best suited to provide in-depth insights into the phenomenon under investigation. A total of 10 nurses participated in the study, all of whom were stationed in the OB-GYN wards at a government regional hospital in Tagum City. To ensure that participants had substantial experience in caring for indigenous clients, only nurses with more than three years of service were included. This criterion was chosen to ensure that the participants had encountered a variety of situations involving transcultural nursing and could provide rich, reflective accounts of their experiences. By focusing on these experienced nurses, the study aimed to capture a deeper understanding of the challenges and rewards involved in providing care to indigenous populations within the hospital setting.

Data Collection Procedure

The data collection for this study followed a systematic and rigorous process. First, approval was obtained from the Master of Arts in Nursing Program Chair at Davao Doctors College, Inc. to initiate the research. Following this, the guide questions for the in-depth interviews were submitted to three research experts for validation, ensuring the credibility, clarity, and acceptability of the interview protocol. Once validated, permission was sought from the Medical Center Chief of the research setting to conduct the study within the hospital.

Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participating nurses, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose and their voluntary participation. The data were then gathered through in-depth interviews, with each session being audio-recorded to ensure accuracy and completeness of the data. After the interviews, the recordings were transcribed verbatim to capture the participants' responses accurately.

The transcribed data were analyzed using Colaizzi's method of thematic analysis, a structured approach that involves a detailed examination of the participants' accounts to extract meaningful themes (Shosha, 2012). To ensure the validity of the findings, the generated themes were presented to the participants for re-evaluation as a final validation step. This allowed the researcher to confirm that the themes accurately reflected the participants' intended messages and experiences.

Trustworthiness of the Study

Ensuring the trustworthiness of this phenomenological study was vital in validating the findings and establishing the rigor of the research process. The study adhered to the criteria of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability, as outlined by Lincoln and Guba (1985), to ensure the reliability and integrity of the results.

To enhance credibility, the researcher employed several strategies. Prolonged engagement and persistent observation were key to building rapport with participants and gaining a deep understanding of their lived experiences. Spending sufficient time with the participants allowed for the collection of rich, detailed data. Additionally, member checking was conducted by inviting participants to review the transcriptions and preliminary findings to ensure that the interpretations accurately reflected their experiences. This validation process strengthened the accuracy and credibility of the study's conclusions. Peer debriefing was another important strategy, where colleagues and qualitative research experts reviewed the findings, providing external scrutiny that further bolstered the credibility of the research process.

Transferability was achieved by providing rich, thick descriptions of the research context, participants, and findings. By offering detailed insights into the hospital setting, the cultural dynamics, and the demographics of the indigenous clients and the nurses, the study allows readers to assess the relevance and applicability of the findings to other similar

contexts. This approach ensures that the conclusions drawn from this study can be evaluated for potential application in other settings or populations, thereby enhancing the study's value in broader transcultural nursing practice.

Dependability was maintained through careful documentation of each phase of the research process. An audit trail was created to provide a transparent, detailed record of the steps followed, including the decisions made during data collection, coding, and analysis. This meticulous documentation enables external reviewers to assess the consistency and reliability of the study's findings. The researcher also practiced reflexivity by maintaining a reflexive journal throughout the study, which documented personal reflections, biases, and decisions. This reflexive practice helped manage and account for any potential influences that may have impacted the research process or interpretations, ensuring the research remained objective and transparent.

Confirmability was ensured by minimizing researcher bias and maintaining a clear focus on the participants' lived experiences. Reflexive journaling helped the researcher track personal biases and assumptions, ensuring that the findings were grounded in the participants' perspectives rather than preconceived notions. Triangulation, which involved corroborating data through multiple sources (e.g., participant validation and peer review), and maintaining an audit trail, further strengthened confirmability by demonstrating that the study's conclusions were derived directly from the data, thus enhancing the objectivity and transparency of the research.

By rigorously applying these criteria, the study achieved credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. This comprehensive approach to trustworthiness reinforced the validity of the research, ensuring that the findings provide a robust, trustworthy contribution to understanding the lived experiences of nurses caring for indigenous populations at the government regional hospital located in Barangay Apokon, Tagum City, Davao del Norte.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to rigorous ethical principles to safeguard the rights, dignity, and well-being of all participants. Prior to commencement, the study was thoroughly reviewed and approved by the technical panel of the Master of Arts in Nursing Program at Davao Doctors College, Inc. Additionally, the legal counsel of the research setting conducted an independent review to confirm that there were no legal impediments to conducting the research. This dual-layered evaluation ensured that the study complied with established ethical standards and guidelines, adding an extra measure of oversight and accountability.

Participants were fully informed about the purpose, objectives, procedures, and potential risks and benefits of the study. The process of obtaining informed consent was conducted with utmost transparency, ensuring that participants understood their rights, including the right to withdraw from the study at any point without facing any repercussions. By securing voluntary and informed consent, the study upheld the ethical principles of autonomy and

respect for individual rights, ensuring that participants were empowered in their decision to participate.

Confidentiality was strictly maintained throughout the research process. The identities of participants were protected by anonymizing all data, ensuring that personal identifiers were removed from transcripts and related materials. This prevented any potential identification of participants in the study results or publications. Data security was a top priority, with all information stored on password-protected devices, accessible only to the researcher and authorized personnel. These steps ensured that sensitive information shared during the study remained secure, preserving the participants' privacy.

Ethical data management procedures were also carefully observed. All digital data were securely stored on password-protected systems and backed up to ensure there was no risk of data loss or unauthorized access. Physical data, such as handwritten notes and transcripts, were kept in locked storage and later securely disposed of, with transcripts shredded and digital files permanently deleted using specialized software. This ensured that the participants' information remained confidential and protected throughout the research and post-research phases.

The study was guided by the ethical principle of beneficence, which prioritizes the well-being of participants and seeks to maximize the potential benefits of the research. The study aimed to generate valuable insights into the lived experiences of nurses caring for indigenous clients, which could lead to improved support systems, policies, and practices within the healthcare field. This focus on beneficence not only ensured the ethical integrity of the study but also aimed to create meaningful contributions to nursing practice, particularly in addressing the challenges of transcultural nursing.

By adhering to these ethical standards—covering informed consent, confidentiality, data security, and beneficence—the study ensured the protection and respect of its participants while contributing valuable knowledge to the nursing community.

RESULTS

Profile of the Informants

The respondents of this study were purposively selected based on their professional experience and direct involvement in caring for indigenous clients at the research setting. A total of 10 nurses participated, all of whom were stationed in the OB-GYN wards of the hospital. These nurses were chosen due to their extensive exposure to the unique cultural and healthcare needs of indigenous patients, as well as their ability to provide rich insights into the complexities of transcultural nursing.

To ensure that participants had substantial experience in the field, one of the key inclusion criteria was a minimum of three years of service in the research setting. This threshold was established to guarantee that the respondents had sufficient experience to reflect on

their encounters with indigenous clients and provide meaningful contributions to the study. Their prolonged involvement in patient care allowed them to navigate and address the challenges posed by language barriers, cultural differences, and traditional health practices, making them well-positioned to offer valuable perspectives on transcultural nursing.

The diversity of the respondents' backgrounds—both in terms of their own cultural experiences and their professional roles—also contributed to the richness of the data. All participants were registered nurses with varying degrees of experience in maternal and child health, which is a key service area for indigenous populations seeking care at the research setting. Their hands-on experience, combined with their professional training, enabled them to effectively manage the healthcare needs of indigenous clients while balancing the complexities of cultural sensitivity and clinical care.

Overall, the respondents provided a wide range of insights into the lived realities of nurses practicing transcultural nursing in a government hospital setting. Their profiles reflect a deep commitment to patient care, particularly in addressing the health disparities faced by indigenous communities, and they served as key informants in understanding the challenges and rewards of this unique nursing practice.

Figure 1. *Thematic map*

Theme 1: Confronting the Realities

The first emergent theme, *Confronting the Realities*, encapsulates the challenges nurses face while providing care to patients from different cultural backgrounds, specifically indigenous communities. Nursing is inherently demanding, and the complexities are further amplified when nurses care for patients whose cultural beliefs and practices may conflict with standard medical care. This theme reflects the difficult realities of transcultural nursing, where language barriers and cultural differences significantly impact the quality of healthcare delivery.

Nurses are trained to provide care to all patients, regardless of age, gender, religion, or ethnicity. However, this non-selective approach means they frequently encounter patients whose cultural practices may challenge the norms of medical treatment. These encounters often highlight two central difficulties in transcultural nursing: 1) *Gambala sa Pakikipag-usap*: Facing Language Barriers, and 2) *Salungat sa Paniniwala*: Conflicts in Cultural Beliefs and Practices. These sub-themes illustrate the core struggles nurses face when caring for indigenous clients, particularly in navigating communication and cultural beliefs that may diverge from Western medical practices.

Cluster Theme 1: *Gambala sa Pakikipag-usap*: Facing Language Barriers

Effective communication is the foundation of quality healthcare, and transcultural nursing is no exception. However, when nurses and indigenous patients do not share a common language or dialect, miscommunication becomes a significant obstacle. This cluster theme, *Gambala sa Pakikipag-usap* (which translates to “disturbances in communication”), explores the challenges that arise from language barriers in healthcare settings.

Participants unanimously identified language barriers as one of the primary hindrances to providing quality care for indigenous clients. Miscommunication often made it difficult to reach a mutual understanding, which in turn hindered the effectiveness of health education and the implementation of care plans. Some nurses shared how they resorted to non-verbal communication, such as acting out instructions, to bridge the gap, yet these efforts were often insufficient.

For example, one nurse expressed frustration over her failed attempts to make a patient understand despite her extensive efforts:

"There really are times that it becomes very difficult for me to make them understand about these teachings, and I even got to the point of acting out what I wanted them to understand just to ensure that they'd follow my instructions. Indeed, language barrier is undeniably apparent." (Participant 3)

Participants also highlighted how this communication breakdown led to feelings of helplessness, as nurses struggled to convey essential health information. The use of interpreters, either from fellow staff members or the patient's family, was suggested as a possible solution. However, participants acknowledged that interpreters were not always available, making this an inconsistent and temporary fix:

"Some indigenous clients have relatives/watchers that know how to speak Visaya, and so, in these cases, we'd ask these relatives to help us in the translation and provision of health teachings." (Participant 3)

This issue emphasizes the significant challenges posed by language barriers in healthcare. The inability to communicate effectively often leads to misunderstandings that can negatively impact patient outcomes, particularly when patients fail to follow self-care instructions or adhere to medication regimens due to miscommunication.

Cluster Theme 2: *Salungat sa Paniniwala*: Conflicts in Cultural Beliefs and Practices

Another major challenge in transcultural nursing is navigating the cultural beliefs and practices of indigenous clients that may contradict medical recommendations. *Salungat sa Paniniwala* (translated as “opposing beliefs”) explores the conflicts nurses encounter when indigenous patients’ cultural practices do not align with medically prescribed treatments.

Participants frequently encountered resistance from patients who, due to their cultural beliefs, refused to comply with medical interventions. For example, one nurse shared an experience where a patient refused to bathe after surgery due to the belief that bathing would worsen her condition:

“One time, I had a patient who was post-TAHBSO that did not take a bath for days. She became unkempt and disheveled, so I advised her to take a bath. However, she refused, saying that bathing would make her sicker.” (Participant 3)

Such instances reflect the tension between traditional cultural beliefs and modern medical practices. Nurses also noted that in addition to health-related non-compliance, indigenous clients often hold distinct cultural practices, such as refraining from physical contact during assessments or vital sign checks, which further complicates the delivery of care:

“...I have encountered an indigenous patient who did not want to be touched because the act of touching others is not a custom [where she was raised].” (Participant 3)

Cultural beliefs and practices can significantly affect patient compliance and the nurse-patient relationship, making it essential for healthcare providers to practice cultural sensitivity and respect. To such end, nurses in this study expressed the need for patience and understanding when dealing with these cultural conflicts. They recognized the importance of finding ways to bridge the gap between medically accepted practices and culturally appropriate care, a theme that will be further explored in the subsequent sections.

The themes of *Gambala sa Pakikipag-usap* and *Salungat sa Paniniwala* illustrate the dual challenges nurses face in transcultural nursing: overcoming language barriers and navigating conflicts between medical protocols and indigenous cultural practices. Together, these challenges underscore the importance of cultural competence in healthcare and the need for ongoing efforts to address these realities in nursing practice.

Theme 2: Linking Two Worlds

The second emergent theme, *Linking Two Worlds*, reflects the inherent challenge of integrating the scientific world of medicine with the rich, diverse world of indigenous culture. This theme addresses the nurses’ efforts to reconcile the often-conflicting practices of modern healthcare with the deeply rooted cultural beliefs of their indigenous clients. The task of linking these two worlds—medical science and cultural traditions—requires a delicate balance, as nurses strive to provide effective healthcare while respecting the cultural identities of their patients.

This theme highlights the ongoing efforts by nurses to bridge the gap between these two domains. The nurses' experiences are encapsulated in two sub-themes: 1) *Tiyaga at Pag-unawa*: Imbibing Patience and Understanding, and 2) *Pagdurugtong sa Kakulangan*: Bridging the Gap.

Cluster Theme 1: *Tiyaga at Pag-unawa*: Imbibing Patience and Understanding

Addressing language barriers and navigating differences in cultural beliefs and practices can be an overwhelming task for nurses, requiring constant patience and understanding. The sub-theme *Tiyaga at Pag-unawa* (which translates to “patience and understanding”) explores how nurses continually exercise these virtues to manage the complexities of caring for indigenous clients.

Participants shared that caring for indigenous patients can be particularly demanding due to cultural and communication barriers. Many emphasized that patience is not only a necessity but also a fundamental part of providing care in these circumstances. Nurses often must go beyond their usual routines, demonstrating empathy and cultural sensitivity to ensure that indigenous clients feel respected and understood. One nurse articulated the importance of patience in overcoming communication hurdles:

"[Taking] care [of] indigenous clients needs a lot of patience and understanding, [since we, as nurses, should consider the existence of the differences in our] cultural beliefs and practices, not to mention the communication barrier..." (Participant 1)

Participants also emphasized the importance of understanding the cultural nuances that affect their patients' health behaviors. By exercising patience and maintaining an open mind, nurses can navigate cultural practices that may conflict with medical recommendations. These responses underscore the importance of building trust and fostering an environment where indigenous patients feel their cultural identities are acknowledged and respected:

"[On top of that, these patients are also devoted to their culture and beliefs, and, to that end, it takes a lot of patience, humility, and understanding to let them practice their beliefs while ensuring that they are safe, and they receive the best care possible." (Participant 10)

This sentiment highlights the role of patience and understanding in effective communication across cultural boundaries. Nurses who demonstrate these qualities are more likely to foster trusting relationships with their patients, which is essential for delivering culturally sensitive care.

Cluster Theme 2: *Pagdurugtong sa Kakulangan*: Bridging the Gap

In addition to practicing patience and understanding, nurses also expressed the need to actively bridge the gap in their knowledge and skills when caring for indigenous clients. The sub-theme *Pagdurugtong sa Kakulangan* (translated as “bridging the gap”) reflects the participants' efforts to fill in the gaps in their understanding of indigenous cultures and practices, thereby enhancing their ability to provide culturally appropriate care.

Many participants acknowledged that despite their years of service, they often felt inadequate in their ability to provide culturally sensitive care. Miscommunication and cultural conflicts still posed significant challenges in their daily interactions with indigenous clients. This sentiment is reflected in the statement of one nurse who highlighted the need for healthcare providers to continually learn about the cultural backgrounds of their patients:

"As healthcare providers, we should learn more about these clients' background and their cultural beliefs [and practices], and this includes learning about their dialects, in order for us to better render nursing care to them..." (Participant 2)

Another nurse suggested that nursing education should include more in-depth training on indigenous cultures, as this knowledge would help nurses navigate the complexities of transcultural nursing more effectively:

"...We, as nurses, need to learn more about the indigenous population because I feel that, even though they have existed in our country for many years already, they still haven't received the focus that they deserve... It would be better if studying their culture will be included in our curriculum." (Participant 2)

Despite the challenges, participants expressed a strong commitment to continuous learning and improving their capacity to care for indigenous clients. This perseverance, they believed, was key to bridging the cultural gap and providing optimal care. As one participant emphasized:

"Based on my experience, I think there is a need for a nurse to learn about the different cultures [and] practices of the different tribes in the different municipalities and provinces, [so that one would] be equipped in handling IP clients." (Participant 1)

The need for continuous learning about different cultures is echoed in such passage, further stressing that learning about a patient's cultural background fosters understanding and empathy, which are critical for developing trust and providing effective healthcare. By investing time and effort in learning about their patients' cultural practices, nurses can bridge the gap between medical care and cultural understanding, enhancing both patient satisfaction and health outcomes.

In summary, *Linking Two Worlds* highlights the ongoing efforts of nurses to balance the scientific aspects of medical care with the cultural practices of their indigenous patients. Through patience, understanding, and a commitment to learning, nurses strive to overcome the barriers posed by language and cultural differences. These efforts are essential in transcultural nursing, as they enable healthcare providers to deliver care that is not only medically appropriate but also culturally respectful and inclusive.

Theme 3: Being One with Every Juan

The third emergent theme, *Being One with Every Juan*, reflects the unifying experiences of nurses who, despite the diversity in their patients' cultural backgrounds, find joy and fulfillment in providing care to indigenous clients. The term "Juan" symbolizes every Filipino, but in this theme, it signifies a broader concept of unity and harmony, where differences are embraced rather than divided. This theme focuses on the profound sense of purpose nurses experience in transcultural nursing, showcasing how diverse worlds can come together in healthcare.

This theme is explored through two sub-themes: 1) *Tagumpay sa Pag-agapay*: Fulfillment in Being a Nurse to Indigenous Clients, and 2) *Pagkakaisa sa Pagkakaiba-iba*: Unity in Diversity.

Cluster Theme 1: *Tagumpay sa Pag-agapay*: Fulfillment in Being a Nurse to Indigenous Clients

Despite the challenges posed by language barriers and cultural differences, the nurses participating in this study consistently expressed a deep sense of fulfillment in their role as caregivers to indigenous clients. The sub-theme *Tagumpay sa Pag-agapay* (which translates to "success in supporting others") highlights the emotional rewards that come with successfully delivering care and seeing positive outcomes in their patients' health.

Participants shared that their greatest joy comes from witnessing their indigenous clients improve and adhere to medical advice, despite the initial difficulties in communication and cultural understanding. One nurse explained how convincing a patient to overcome her cultural belief against bathing after surgery brought her a sense of accomplishment:

"[What I consider as a] joy... is when I get to successfully convince my patient to follow what I taught them to do... convincing her into thinking that taking a bath is not a bad thing made me happy. She even verbalized her realization that bathing is, in fact, not at all bad and that she felt much better after taking one." (Participant 3)

Nurses also found fulfillment in imparting health education to their indigenous clients, often considering this one of the most rewarding aspects of their work. One participant described the joy of seeing her patients leave the hospital not only healthier but also more knowledgeable about the care they received:

"[I feel] joy... in giving them the best services that I can, imparting them all the necessary education based on their level of understanding, and then seeing them be discharged healthy..." (Participant 5)

In addition to the professional satisfaction of providing care, participants noted the respect, politeness, and courtesy they received from indigenous clients, which they found particularly uplifting. These qualities stood out as rare and meaningful expressions of gratitude, helping to reinforce the nurses' positive sense of self-worth in their role:

"...some of my indigenous clients are very respectful, polite, and courteous..." (Participant 3)

This sense of fulfillment highlights the positive relationship between cultural competence in nursing and job satisfaction. When nurses incorporate cultural values into patient care, it leads to greater satisfaction for both the patient and the healthcare provider, fostering a more meaningful and enriching relationship.

Cluster Theme 2: *Pagkakaisa sa Pagkakaiba-iba*: Unity in Diversity

Nursing is a profession that inherently embraces diversity, as healthcare providers are responsible for caring for individuals from various cultural, ethnic, and social backgrounds. The sub-theme *Pagkakaisa sa Pagkakaiba-iba* (translated as "unity in diversity") captures the nurses' recognition of the importance of integrating their patients' cultural beliefs into care, fostering unity and respect for diversity in their practice.

Participants expressed the realization that true patient care requires acknowledging and incorporating the cultural beliefs and practices of their indigenous clients. They emphasized that ignoring these differences can render their care ineffective, while understanding and respecting cultural diversity leads to more meaningful and effective nursing:

"Personally, I see taking care of indigenous clients as an eye opener, a realization that each individual is unique..." (Participant 2)

Another nurse emphasized the importance of not being judgmental and approaching each patient with cultural sensitivity, regardless of their background. This sentiment reflects the idea that diversity should not only be acknowledged but celebrated, as it enriches the nurse-patient relationship:

"We should not be judgmental, and we should listen to their concerns, whoever they are and what society they belong to." (Participant 7)

Participants shared that their experiences caring for indigenous clients have deepened their understanding of cultural diversity, helping them appreciate the uniqueness of each patient. In doing so, they also realized that many indigenous practices are not necessarily in conflict with modern medical care, but can complement it when integrated thoughtfully:

"What I can share [to my colleagues] is that indigenous are unique individuals who have and believe in different cultural beliefs and practices, and in discovering these differences, we can actually see that not all of their practices are inappropriate or detrimental..." (Participant 9)

These reflections emphasize the value of cultural competence in healthcare, further stressing that healthcare providers who embrace cultural diversity and approach their patients with sensitivity and openness are better equipped to deliver high-quality care, which in turn fosters positive health outcomes and stronger nurse-patient relationships.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this phenomenological study was to explore the lived experiences of nurses caring for indigenous clients at the government regional hospital in Tagum City. Specifically, the study focused on understanding the challenges, rewards, and complexities of transcultural nursing in this unique healthcare setting. Through in-depth interviews, three major themes emerged: *Confronting the Realities*, *Linking Two Worlds*, and *Being One with Every Juan*. These themes reveal the complexities of transcultural nursing and highlight the importance of cultural competence, communication, and empathy in the delivery of healthcare services to indigenous populations.

The study's findings indicate that nurses face significant challenges when caring for indigenous clients, primarily due to language barriers and conflicting cultural beliefs and practices. However, the nurses also expressed a sense of fulfillment in their roles, finding joy and meaning in successfully navigating these challenges and providing culturally sensitive care. Furthermore, the nurses emphasized the need for patience, understanding, and continuous learning to bridge the gap between modern medical practices and indigenous cultural beliefs. These key findings align with previous research that underscores the importance of cultural competence in healthcare settings (Atanga & Ayong, 2017; Berman et al., 2016; Betancourt, 2006).

The first theme, *Confronting the Realities*, highlighted the nurses' struggles with language barriers and cultural conflicts. Participants described the difficulty in communicating with indigenous clients who often spoke dialects unfamiliar to the nurses. Miscommunication was a significant barrier to providing effective care, as patients frequently failed to understand self-care instructions or medical interventions. This finding aligns with previous literature, which identifies language barriers as a major obstacle in transcultural healthcare (Horrill et al., 2018; Peiris et al., 2008; Stephens et al., 2005). According to Meuter et al. (2015), miscommunication in healthcare can be life-threatening, making it imperative for healthcare providers to address language barriers effectively. Addressing communication gaps is crucial, especially as healthcare providers serve clients from diverse indigenous, ethnic, and racial groups (McCalman et al., 2017).

Additionally, the nurses encountered conflicts between medical protocols and the indigenous clients' cultural beliefs and practices. For example, some clients refused to bathe after surgery due to cultural beliefs that bathing would worsen their condition. Such conflicts reflect broader challenges in transcultural nursing, where Western medical practices often clash with traditional beliefs (UNDP, 2013). Despite these challenges, the nurses demonstrated a strong commitment to providing care, highlighting the importance of empathy and cultural sensitivity in overcoming these obstacles.

The second theme, *Linking Two Worlds*, emphasized the nurses' efforts to bridge the gap between modern medicine and indigenous culture. This theme underscores the importance of patience and understanding, as nurses often had to navigate complex cultural dynamics to provide care that was both effective and respectful of the clients' beliefs. Participants described the need to adapt their approach to care, incorporating

indigenous cultural practices into their treatment plans whenever possible. This approach aligns with Leininger's theory of transcultural nursing, which advocates for culturally congruent care that respects the cultural values and beliefs of patients (Berman et al., 2016).

Participants also acknowledged their own limitations in understanding indigenous cultures and expressed a desire for continuous learning. They recognized that their ability to provide culturally competent care was still developing and that further education on indigenous cultures could enhance their effectiveness as nurses. This finding echoes the literature, which emphasizes the need for healthcare providers to receive ongoing training in cultural competence to improve patient outcomes (Tervalon & Murray-García, 1998). These findings are particularly relevant as indigenous populations often face systemic barriers, leading to inequitable healthcare experiences (Horrill et al., 2018; Torres-Ruiz et al., 2018).

The third theme, *Being One with Every Juan*, revealed the fulfillment nurses experienced in caring for indigenous clients, despite the challenges. Nurses found joy in seeing their patients recover and comply with medical advice, especially after overcoming communication and cultural barriers. This sense of fulfillment is consistent with research showing that culturally competent nursing care can lead to increased job satisfaction and better nurse-patient relationships (Atanga & Ayong, 2017). Participants also appreciated the respect and politeness they received from their indigenous clients, which contributed to their positive sense of self-worth and professional pride.

This theme also highlighted the nurses' realization of the importance of unity in diversity. They emphasized the need to integrate patients' cultural beliefs into care and to view cultural diversity as an opportunity for growth and learning. This insight aligns with the broader concept of cultural humility, which encourages healthcare providers to approach each patient with openness and respect for their unique cultural perspectives. By embracing cultural differences, the nurses were able to foster stronger relationships with their indigenous clients and provide more meaningful care (Tervalon & Murray-García, 1998). This is particularly important given that indigenous peoples remain one of the most marginalized groups in the Philippines and globally (UNDP, 2013; United Nations, 2014).

Implications of the Findings

The findings of this study have significant implications for both nursing practice and healthcare policy. First, the study highlights the critical role of cultural competence in delivering effective healthcare to indigenous populations. Nurses need to be equipped with the skills and knowledge necessary to navigate cultural differences, particularly in regions with diverse indigenous communities like the Philippines. This calls for the integration of more comprehensive cultural competency training in nursing education and ongoing professional development programs.

Furthermore, the study underscores the importance of addressing language barriers in healthcare settings. Hospitals should consider employing multilingual staff or providing

language interpretation services to ensure effective communication with indigenous clients. Failure to address these barriers can result in poor health outcomes, as seen in the experiences shared by the participants (Meuter et al., 2015).

The study also contributes to the growing body of research on transcultural nursing, providing valuable insights into the lived experiences of nurses working with indigenous populations. These findings support the existing literature on the need for culturally congruent care (Leininger, 2001, as cited in Busher Betancourt, 2015) and highlight the importance of continuous learning and adaptability in transcultural nursing practice.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the lived experiences of nurses caring for indigenous clients in a government hospital setting. The findings reveal the complex challenges of transcultural nursing, particularly in overcoming language barriers and cultural conflicts. Despite these challenges, nurses expressed a deep sense of fulfillment in their work, finding joy and meaning in providing culturally sensitive care.

This study emphasizes the critical need for ongoing cultural competence training in nursing, particularly for those working with diverse populations. It also highlights the importance of bridging communication gaps through language support services. Ultimately, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of the significance of culturally congruent care and provides a foundation for future research and policy development in transcultural nursing.

Limitations of the Study

While this study provides valuable insights into the experiences of nurses caring for indigenous clients, there are several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the study was limited to a single healthcare facility, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings to other settings. Additionally, the sample size was relatively small, consisting of only 10 participants, which may not fully capture the diversity of experiences among nurses working with indigenous populations. Future research could expand the scope of the study by including multiple healthcare settings and a larger sample size to gain a more comprehensive understanding of transcultural nursing.

Another limitation is the potential for bias in self-reported data. The participants' accounts of their experiences were based on their perceptions, which may have been influenced by social desirability or recall bias. However, efforts were made to mitigate this by employing member checking to validate the accuracy of the findings.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made for nursing practice and future research. First, there is a clear need for healthcare institutions to provide ongoing cultural competence training for nurses, with a specific focus on

indigenous populations. This training should include not only language skills but also a deeper understanding of cultural beliefs and practices that may impact healthcare delivery.

Hospitals and healthcare organizations should also consider implementing language support services, such as interpreters, to overcome communication barriers with indigenous clients. Additionally, incorporating transcultural nursing theories, such as Leininger's theory, into nursing curricula can help future nurses develop the skills necessary to provide culturally congruent care.

Future research should explore the experiences of nurses in different healthcare settings, particularly in rural areas where indigenous populations are more concentrated. Investigating the perspectives of indigenous patients themselves could also provide a more holistic understanding of the challenges and opportunities in transcultural nursing.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in strict adherence to ethical standards throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's objectives, procedures, and potential implications. Participants were also explicitly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time, without any negative consequences. This measure guaranteed that participation was entirely voluntary and that participants retained autonomy over their involvement.

To protect the privacy and confidentiality of the participants, all personal identifiers were removed from the data. Anonymity was rigorously maintained, ensuring that none of the information provided could be traced back to any individual participant. The well-being of the participants was prioritized, with efforts made to minimize any potential distress or discomfort that could arise during the interview process. If any issues of discomfort were identified, the researcher took immediate steps to mitigate them and ensure that the participants felt supported.

There were no conflicts of interest in the conduct of this study. The researcher adhered strictly to ethical guidelines to prevent plagiarism, ensuring that all referenced sources were properly cited and credited in accordance with academic standards. Objectivity was maintained in the analysis of the data, ensuring that the findings were presented without bias, and that they accurately reflected the experiences shared by the participants. The results of this study were used exclusively for research purposes, contributing to the broader understanding of transcultural nursing and informing best practices in caring for indigenous clients.

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